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ABSTRACT

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Aloqa uchun:

Telefon: +99899 011 6303

E pochta: scienceshine@mail.ru

[ru](mailto:scienceshine@mail.ru)

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METHODS OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH

Jaloliddin Kosimov Abduvali ugli

Doctoral student (PhD) of Namangan Foreign Languages Institute, Teacher of
Learning Skills lab learning center
kosimovjaloliddin5@gmail.com

Annotation: In this article there is considered about the communicative method of learning a foreign language as this method is a set of techniques designed to teach effective communication in a language environment. Some methods of improving students' communicative competence in English are discussed below.

Keywords: Communicative competence, dialogue of cultures, video lesson, performance lesson, cultural material, excursion lesson, psychological characteristics, creative opportunities.

The transition to an information society requires the full development of the individual, including his communication skills, which facilitate entry into the world community and allow him to function successfully in it. A school graduate must have the necessary skills and abilities for this, i.e. knowledge that make up a holistic picture of the world, skills and abilities to carry out different types of activities: educational, labor, aesthetic, as well as to have modern value orientations and experience of creative activity, to be able to use new information technologies, to be ready for interpersonal and intercultural cooperation, both within your own country and internationally.

Language, native or foreign, serves as a means of communication, allowing people to interact with each other, to influence each other in the natural conditions of social life. The culture of communication is a complex, multifaceted and multifaceted education. The culture of communication is formed in the process of education and continues continuously throughout a person's life. The modern school plays an important role not only in education, but also in the upbringing of a general culture, the formation of a culture of communication, a communicative culture of the individual. The search for the best forms and methods of developing a culture of communication was carried out earlier and is being carried out at the present time by many domestic teachers, psychologists and scientists. The problem of human

upbringing and the upbringing of a culture of communication, in particular, are one of the most significant at this stage of development of the education system. English, as the language of international communication, acts as an instrument of communication in the dialogue of all cultures of the modern world and presupposes the acquisition of foreign language communicative competence by students. In the development and education of the ability and readiness for independent and continuous study of the English language, further self-education with its help, the leading role today is assigned to the formation and development of linguistic, speech and socio-cultural competencies in order to:

- in order to form in schoolchildren the necessary skills and abilities in one form or another of speech activity, as well as language competence, active oral practice is necessary for each student;

- in order to form communicative competence, it is not enough to enrich the lesson with communication exercises. It is important to provide an opportunity for students to think freely, to solve any problems that give rise to thought, to discuss various possibilities for solving these problems, so that students focus their attention on the content of their statement, so that the focus is on thought, and language appears in its direct function - the formation and formulation of these thoughts;

- in order for students to perceive the language as a means of intercultural interaction, it is necessary to look for ways to include them in an active dialogue of cultures, so that they can learn in practice the peculiarities of the functioning of the language in a new culture for them.

Communicativeness presupposes the speech orientation of the educational process, which consists in the practical use of the language. Practical speech orientation, not only an end, but also a means to achieve this end.

Based on the communicative approach, in the process of teaching English, it is necessary for students to acquire communicative competence.

Communicative competence implies the ability to use all types of speech activity: reading, speaking, listening, and writing. Communication competence also includes language competence, socio-cultural knowledge, skills and abilities. Linguistic competence means the ability to express one's thoughts or understand the thoughts of others using linguistic means that is, the ability and skills to use vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation for speech activity. To achieve mutual understanding, knowledge of the socio-cultural context, skills and abilities of verbal and non-verbal behavior typical of native speakers are also required.

Thus, communicative competence is an “integrative” concept (A.A. , that is, the reception and transmission of information using different types of speech activity.

The communicative method of teaching foreign languages is one of the most popular in the world today. It is considered by many to be the most progressive and most effective. The communicative method appeared in the 60s and 70s in Britain, when the English language gradually began to acquire the status of the language of international communication. It was then that it became clear that the tried and true traditional methods of that time were no longer satisfying the needs of most foreigners studying English.

This method is a set of techniques designed to teach effective communication in a language environment. Most of them have been used in the classroom before. One of its main techniques is to imitate real-life situations, designed to stimulate students to actively "speak". At the same time, it is very important that the topics are topical, related to the everyday life of students, the problems that occupy them. In classes conducted according to the communicative method, the course of the lesson depends on the students themselves - their answers, reactions, etc. Since communication takes place meaningfully, on appropriate topics. Of course, most of the classes are spoken, although reading and writing are studied too. Teachers generally do not speak, but listen and direct the course of the lesson.

The purpose of learning English is the development of foreign language communicative competence in the aggregate of all its components - speech, language, socio- cultural, compensatory, educational and cognitive. It should be noted the importance of developing and educating schoolchildren of the need to use a foreign language as a means of communication, cognition, self-realization and social adaptation. If we talk about the educational role of learning a foreign language, then it is important here - the education of the qualities of a citizen, a patriot; development of national identity, striving for mutual understanding between people of different communities; tolerant attitude to manifestations of another culture.

The formation and development of communicative competence in the classroom should be carried out through a system of exercises in all types of speech activity. Learning-speech situations and game technologies should become the fundamental elements of the system of exercises.

Game technologies include a large group of techniques and methods of organizing the pedagogical process. Play is a way to communicate.

Game moments in the classroom help to activate the desire of students to contact with each other and the teacher. Finger theater, for example, helps create fun, live communication.

Using elements of developmental teaching, controlling tasks, taking into account the psychological characteristics of children's learning, the teacher tries to develop the cognitive activity of schoolchildren, create conditions for the development of creative opportunities, carefully selecting the forms and methods of teaching. These are travel lessons, game lessons, lecture lessons, discussion lessons, etc. Elements of amusement and surprise form solid knowledge and skills and are aimed at developing reading, speaking and listening skills, relieve fatigue and stress, make lessons more lively, interesting ... If, in order to achieve success in a game, a child needs to perform some kind of speech action, then it is mastered practically without effort. Play creates a wonderful natural environment for language acquisition, it helps language acquisition at any age. In addition, participation in the game increases children's interest in learning English, they have a desire to improve their knowledge of the subject, overcome the psychological barrier - fear. All students, even the weakest, take part in the game, and this is a great success if there is not a single indifferent, passive student in the class.

An effective and productive form of teaching is a performance lesson. Preparing a play is a creative work that contributes to the development of children's language communication skills and the disclosure of their individual creative abilities. This type of work activates the thinking and speech activity of students, develops their interest in literature, serves to better assimilate the culture of the country of the target language, and also deepens the knowledge of the language, since this is the process of memorizing vocabulary.

Using a video lesson to develop communicative competence. It is very difficult to master the communicative competence in English without being in the country of the target language, therefore the important task of the teacher is to create real and imaginary situations of communication in a foreign language lesson using various methods of work. For this purpose, authentic materials, including videos, are essential. The use of the video also helps the development of various aspects of the mental activity of students, first of all, attention and memory.

The next method of developing communicative competence is the use of a lesson-excursion: in our time, when ties between different countries and peoples are developing more and more, acquaintance with Russian national culture becomes a necessary element of the process of teaching a foreign language. The student should

be able to conduct a city tour, tell foreign guests about the originality of Russian culture, etc. The principle of the dialogue of cultures presupposes the use of cultural material about the native country, which allows one to develop the culture of representation of the native country, as well as to form ideas about the culture of the countries of the target language.

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